

Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities Co-design Workshop Report for the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

From 2022, the ARDC has been making a major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities. This work has been done in accordance with the 2016 NCRIS Roadmap and Department of Education commissioned studies. The projects undertaken in this area formed an emerging *HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons*.

In late 2023, the ARDC received the largest ever investment in HASS and Indigenous Research Capability. In Early 2024 we initiated a process of co-design to deliver on an expanded HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons, covering existing and new areas of research infrastructure.

Improving Indigenous Research Capability is aimed at enhancing Indigenous research capabilities and engaging with data custodians to highlight the importance of community involvement in data governance. It seeks to address the complex challenge of management of Indigenous data in Australia due to issues of access, quality, and cultural sensitivity.

The ARDC is co-designing its new infrastructure investments with the research community and other stakeholders to ensure that we create the greatest possible impact. Development of this infrastructure follows the [HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework](#).

The ARDC conducted two co-design workshops in February 2024 to shape plans for this investment opportunity. These workshops were open to all, and were attended by a total of 80 participants from 29 organisations, including Australian universities, AIATSIS, CSIRO, GLAM and Aboriginal landcare organisations, research data providers, Federal Government, and peak bodies. In Workshop 1 we refined our understanding of the challenge to be addressed and found out what outcomes participants hoped to see. In Workshop 2 we explored how the desired outcomes could be achieved within the new infrastructure investment, and discussed requirements and practical considerations for the potential solutions.

THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS

The ARDC is planning major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities.

The 2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap identified avenues to enhance the impact of HASS (Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences) and Indigenous research, proposing improvements in coordinating research infrastructure to facilitate access to and analysis of physical and digital collections. These improvements involve leveraging tools like digitization, aggregation, and interpretation platforms.

Subsequently, the Australian Government Department of Education commissioned three studies to pinpoint investment-ready programs eligible for National Research Infrastructure funding. While not all recommendations from these studies received funding initially, the identified activities demonstrated a high level of readiness to engage with and benefit from the development of a [HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons](#) (RDC).

From 2022-2024 the ARDC-led HASS and Indigenous RDC has implemented a number of these activities, including:

- Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities (IIRC) led by Dist Prof Marcia Langton, University of Melbourne
- Establishing the Language Data Commons of Australia (LDA) led by Prof Michael Haugh, University of Queensland
- Developing Integrated Research Infrastructure for Social Sciences (IRISS) led by A/Prof Steven McEachern, Australian National University
- Creating the Trove Researcher Platform, which comprised Trove Enhancements (led by ANU) and the ARDC Community Data Lab (led by the ARDC)

In 2023, the ARDC received its largest-ever investment in HASS research infrastructure and Indigenous research capability. This \$25 million grant, part of the Australian Government's 2023 National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) Research Infrastructure Investment Plan Funding Round, supplemented by co-investment from national partners, will further establish long-term, national digital research infrastructure to support HASS and Indigenous research data communities in Australia.

Our commitment extends to supporting existing activities such as IIRC, LDA, the Community Data Lab, and Social Sciences while also considering the expansion of the RDC to include new activities for Creative Arts and Media(ted) Data. It has become evident that sustained investment is crucial to scale up these activities and provide coordinated digital research infrastructure meeting the needs of humanities, arts, social sciences, and Indigenous researchers.

Phase 2 aims to consolidate previous efforts, capitalise on synergies between existing and new projects, broaden partnerships and disciplinary coverage, and deepen engagement with the GLAM sector and Indigenous data governance.

In developing new activities, we have considered researcher needs gathered from consultations in 2021 and identified areas with active, coherent communities where research infrastructure can flourish. We have also looked at existing infrastructure that could be bolstered to transition into enduring national assets.

THE IMPROVING INDIGENOUS RESEARCH CAPABILITIES INVESTMENT OPPORTUNITY

The management of Indigenous data in Australia presents a complex challenge due to issues of access, quality, and cultural sensitivity. The absence of a unified data framework hinders collaboration and poses risks of data loss. Legislative and cultural dynamics further complicate the landscape, requiring adaptable strategies. This pressing issue demands immediate attention and a comprehensive resolution due to the unique cultural context and profound significance attributed to Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander data. Urgent intervention is required to implement strategies, technical enhancements, and educational initiatives aimed at rectifying these shortcomings while prioritising the rights and respect owed to Indigenous communities throughout the research and data lifecycle.

The challenge extends beyond immediate concerns, necessitating the establishment of a cohesive and culturally sensitive framework to guide Indigenous data management. Addressing these challenges is essential for preserving cultural heritage and enabling evidence-based policymaking across various disciplines such as Indigenous Studies, Public Health, and Environmental Science.

Improved data infrastructure fosters multidisciplinary collaboration, addressing the Indigenous data challenge requires a holistic and adaptable approach that not only enhances access and management but also upholds Indigenous rights, preserves data integrity, and fosters collaborative knowledge advancement. Across disciplines such as Indigenous Studies, Public Health, Environmental Science, Social Sciences, Education Research, and Policy and Governance, improved data infrastructure promises more accurate understanding, targeted interventions, and evidence-based decision-making. By establishing an Indigenous Research Data Commons, efforts aim to facilitate global collaboration and knowledge sharing while nurturing a more inclusive and respectful future for Indigenous research and data management.

Hence, IIRC is aimed at enhancing Indigenous research capabilities and engaging with data custodians to highlight the importance of community involvement in data governance.

Going into co-design, it was proposed that Phase 2 should include:

- refinement and expansion of the national Indigenous Research Data Catalogue, within the context of a national federated Indigenous data system
- wider application and extension of the Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Spatio-temporal framework to enable organisations, institutions and agencies nationally to enhance Indigenous datasets to improve their contextual and functional application for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander priority setting and decision making

- development of, and adherence to, regulatory frameworks specific to Indigenous data governance principles
- refining, developing and leveraging data repository services to support critical and at-risk Indigenous data holdings identified in Phase 1
- strengthening security & authentication processes for Indigenous research data nationally.
- engagement with a broad range of industries and sectors to augment Phase 1 research translation: embedding best practice training courses, material and resources to be offered across tertiary education institutions nationally
- development of strategies to improve data awareness (capture, usage, visualisation) for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples

OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS

The ARDC is developing this infrastructure in accordance with the HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516606>). This process is designed to create the greatest impact for research and researchers by co-designing the infrastructure with the people who will benefit from it. Development will follow the stages of Problem Identification, Project Shaping, Project Planning, and Endorsement.

Problem Identification has taken place through extensive consultations and information gathering sessions, as described above. By tracking emerging gaps, opportunities, and sectoral trends, the ARDC has identified potential avenues for delivering benefits to the HASS and Indigenous research community. This strategic delineation of opportunities reflects the ARDC's commitment to addressing pertinent challenges and fostering innovation within the HASS and Indigenous research landscape.

The Project Shaping phase was implemented through the two open co-design workshops described below. Workshops were advertised through ARDC newsletters, social media channels and other networks. We sought to involve experts in research practice, disciplinary needs and infrastructure provision to better understand the current challenges faced by stakeholders and the outcomes that they hope to see, and to shape potential solutions that could be provided by the new infrastructure.

Project Planning and Endorsement phases will follow - further information is provided in the “Next Steps” section below.

WORKSHOP 1

The first co-design workshop was held virtually on 2 February 2024. It was attended by 50 participants from 29 organisations. Organisations represented included 18 Australian universities, AIATSIS, and CSIRO, as well as GLAM, Aboriginal landcare and data infrastructure organisations, Federal Government, and peak bodies.

The aim of this first workshop was to refine our understanding of the challenge to be addressed and find out what outcomes participants want to achieve.

Professor Marcia Langton, Professor Kristen Smith, and Levi Murray (University of Melbourne) presented on the challenge, which they summarised with the following problem statement:

“The current landscape of Indigenous data in Australia poses a multifaceted challenge:

- We lack an overarching framework for the governance of Indigenous data throughout the research lifecycle. Without a structured approach, researchers, custodial institutions, and community members currently face ambiguity and inconsistency that drastically impedes the inclusive and respectful collection, management and access of Indigenous data.
- Indigenous data held at custodial institutions is inconsistent in terms of both data quality and metadata standards. These problems limit our ability to understand what data exists, let alone enable interoperability and reuse of data.
- We lack the education and guidance needed to improve both the quality and respectful and ethical handling of Indigenous data.

Addressing these challenges will allow Australia’s Indigenous data to become a valuable resource that benefits research across a range of disciplines, including Indigenous studies and anthropology, public health and epidemiology, environmental science and conservation, the social sciences, education, and policy and governance. Importantly, it will also contribute significantly to preserving cultural heritage, safeguarding rights, and cultivating an equitable and respectful research environment.”

Participants completed a series of discussion activities in breakout groups, and recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Some key themes from the responses are highlighted below - full responses can be found in Appendix 1.

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

- What is the nature of the challenge we are trying to address? Is this stated clearly in the problem statement?
 - Insufficient Indigenous community engagement/ownership/leadership of research and data
 - Challenging to implement good community-led access control
 - Need for an Indigenous-led framework for research
 - Hard to find and access Indigenous data held by institutions
 - Lack of consistency and standards in protocols, data and metadata
 - Data collections are disparate and fragmented
 - Lack of training about Indigenous needs for researchers, and about data management for Indigenous communities
- Who does this challenge affect? (Who needs a solution?)
 - Indigenous people more broadly - and specifically research participants/collaborators
 - Aboriginal Community-Controlled Organisations
 - Researchers and research institutions
 - Government and other users/holders of Indigenous data
 - Policy makers
- What limitations are created by this challenge?
 - Access to the data is limited - including for communities it refers to
 - Data is fragmented and incomplete
 - Culturally contextual information can be lost from data
 - Lack of trust and transparency between researchers and communities
 - Understanding and agreement on data governance requirements is limited
- What could we achieve by addressing it?

- More widespread use of Indigenous data and knowledge
- Protect and preserve culture
- Better governance of Indigenous data
- Rematriation of data
- Better policy
- Who could benefit?
 - Indigenous communities - both Australian and international
 - Researchers and research institutions
 - Government

Activity 2: Outcomes and opportunities

- What outcomes would be beneficial?
 - Methods to improve community consultation in research
 - Partnerships between community, research and industry
 - Community access to data
 - Build and recognise the importance of trust
 - Improved governance
 - Effective metadata
 - Standardisation and consistency of data, protocols, methods
 - Resources and guidance
 - Education and guidance for students
 - Skills and training for Indigenous stakeholders
 - Awareness of appropriate use of data with complex contexts
- What existing infrastructure/activities could we build on?
 - Participants gave an extensive list of existing platforms, organisations and initiatives that could be leveraged - see Appendix 1

Activity 3: Roles and partners

- What other kinds of partners need to be involved?

- Indigenous communities
- Indigenous peak bodies
- Other Indigenous organisations and groups (language centres, sovereignty hubs, etc)
- NCRIS and other data-focused organisations
- What other expertise/resources would benefit the project?
 - Technical expertise
 - Indigenous research expertise
- Whose perspectives and input would make this project better?
 - Indigenous scholars
 - Indigenous research participants and collaborators
 - Indigenous rangers
 - Elders and community leaders
 - Teachers
 - International colleagues doing similar work

WORKSHOP 2

The second co-design workshop was held virtually on 16 February 2024. It was attended by 52 participants from 26 organisations. Organisations represented included 16 Australian universities, AIATSIS, and CSIRO, as well as GLAM and data infrastructure organisations and peak bodies.

The aim of this workshop was to explore how the desired outcomes identified by participants in Workshop 1 could be achieved within the new infrastructure investment, and understand requirements and practical considerations for the potential solutions.

Staff from the ARDC reported back on the key findings from Workshop 1. Based on the responses to the Workshop 1 question “What outcomes would be beneficial”, we drew out four high-level outcome themes:

- "Increase community engagement, input and access to research and its outputs", based on responses about increased community access to data, partnerships between community, research and industry, and methods to improve community consultation in research.

- "Support the appropriate governance of Indigenous data", based on responses about needing guidance on appropriate governance and the importance of trust.
- "Create standards for indigenous data, metadata and research", based on responses about a need for metadata standards and calling for consistency in protocols.
- "Provide training and guidance", based on responses about a need for resources and guidance, training and skills for Indigenous researchers, and improving awareness of how to use data appropriately.

We addressed each of these four outcome themes in turn. For each theme, Professor Kristen Smith and Levi Murray (University of Melbourne) outlined a range of approaches and solutions that could be taken to achieve that outcome. In breakout groups, the workshop participants discussed those approaches, noting any requirements they would have for these approaches to be successful, and any practical considerations to be taken into account. Participants recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Common themes from the responses are recorded below, and full responses are attached in Appendix 2.

Increase community engagement, input and access to research and its outputs

- Approach: Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander representation and engagement
 - Recognise the diversity of communities and individual perspectives
 - Involve communities at the point of research design
 - Consider alternative methods for participation and access
 - Properly acknowledge and compensate Indigenous contributors
- Approach: Accessible knowledge translation of project outputs
 - Work with communities to ensure outputs are of real benefit
 - Balance the need for access with the protection of sensitive data
 - Consider the technical aspects of access - where is data stored, and how is access granted?
 - Be explicit about data ownership arrangements from the start
- Approach: Network building
 - Create communities of practice
 - Provide capacity-building, skills and mentorship for Indigenous researchers and community participants

Support the appropriate governance of Indigenous data

- Approach: Indigenous data governance frameworks
 - Indigenous-led design of governance frameworks
 - Indigenous involvement in implementation of frameworks
 - Enough flexibility in frameworks to handle needs of diverse communities and changes over time
- Approach: Education and capacity building
 - Training informed by an awareness of both Western and traditional knowledge systems
 - Prioritise training that allows people to make the best-informed decisions
 - Training for non-Indigenous researchers, ethics committee members, etc on Indigenous data governance
 - HASS and Indigenous RDC Computational Skills Summer School has been valuable
- Approach: Accessible and appropriate data stewardship and global collaboration
 - There may be multiple possible custodians of the same data
 - Data stewards need tools and platforms to help control access to data - how do we provide and standardise these without centralising them?
 - We can learn from international efforts
 - Must not lose focus of specific Australian needs and context

Create standards for Indigenous data, metadata and research

- Approach: Indigenous-led standard setting
 - Involve a range of different Indigenous perspectives - not just researchers
 - Managing the tension between established standards and data requirements, and standards created from an Indigenous perspective
 - Standards must have enough flexibility to accommodate diversity of Indigenous communities and their requirements
 - When developing standards, have clear goals and timeframes to manage scope
- Approach: Define cultural metadata standards

- Standards must have enough flexibility to accommodate diversity of Indigenous communities and their requirements
- Approach: Define classifications and licensing
 - Be wary of further limiting access to data when seeking to protect it through licensing arrangements

Provide training and guidance

- Approach: Development of training and upskilling resources
 - Consider the needs and starting points of those being trained - different organisations, range of data literacy - and speak to experts in working with those audiences
 - Use a mixture of delivery models - written resources, face-to-face training, etc.
 - Be aware communities are overloaded with training - what is the benefit?
- Approach: Hands-on Indigenous Data Governance training
 - Training for Indigenous people by Indigenous people
 - “Governance” as a term isn’t always well understood
 - Help communities providing data to understand their rights
- Approach: Supportive learning networks
 - Face-to-face knowledge sharing
 - Need a national indigenous researcher network
 - Mentorship programs

NEXT STEPS

The ARDC has worked with the potential project team to develop a draft project plan, released for public feedback alongside the publication of this report. Feedback submissions will close at the end of day, Friday 22 March. To submit feedback on project plans please use the form on the ARDC website. All feedback will be collated and responded to in a published report, alongside an updated project plan taking into account this feedback wherever possible. Work on this project is planned to commence in July 2024.

The development of the resulting infrastructure will involve ongoing public testing and consultation - please make sure you are signed up to the HASS and I newsletter so that you receive notifications about upcoming opportunities to be involved.

If you have any other comments or questions about this process please contact us at hassi.codesign@ardc.edu.au with the subject line "IIRC".

APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP 1 RESPONSES

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What is the nature of the challenge we are trying to address? Is this stated clearly in the problem statement?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It assumes most data exists already as legacy data. Should we be thinking about the data that is being produced everyday online and in gov policy etc. (+1) ● there are two scenarios here: existing "data" of Indigenous peoples, and then future research on and in Indigenous peoples ● Nature of challenge is fragmented and inaccessible data (+1) ● This challenge means that Indigenous quantitative methodologies lack a culturally appropriate framework for integrative data analysis. There is ample work on integrative data analysis internationally which is not reflected in much Indigenous quantitative social science ● Bringing disparate data sources together in a cohesive manner (+3) ● Be an Indigenous led framework (+1) ● Current structures and frameworks are not designed to navigate Indigenous data needs, resulting in poor practice and inconsistent use of data contributing to ongoing omission of needs from policy development and reform (+1) ● The ecological system for Indigenous data lacks a coherent framework, meaning that data is collected at a point in time but it is not readily used for future/other purposes. this limits the usefulness of data for a range of purposes (+1) ● creation of metadata and protocols governing it have, in the past, been written and communicated in very academic terms. who is expected to add the metadata - if Community then language needs to be accessible to broader population (+5) ● Data standards changing over time - lack of resources to update this data to current standards to make it easier to access / find etc ● Policy framework for metadata implementation (+1) ● Tools and workflows for metadata implementation ● Vocabulary development and governance (+1) ● Need workflows and tools that support multiple voices both in terms of vocabularies and in terms of the annotation of cultural assets.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consistency in the approaches used to record data are a problem. It is difficult to have standards across the diverse range of Indigenous data products. (+1) ● Agreements are written in legalese, not beneficial for partners ● Lack of understanding or agreement about what constitutes 'data' (+1) ● Definition of Indigenous Data is so broad as to be unapproachable - how to decide where to start? ● definitions ● HASS data and scientific data are often separated, but this problem applies to both and we need a solution for both ● HASS and sciences are being treated as separate and not interconnected - yet they absolutely are. How to provide crossovers and bridges? (+1) ● While the IIRC is currently aligned within the HASS&I RDC it does not only deal with HASS data - it is looking at ALL types of data ● Gap in Community knowledge and engagement on issues of data (+1) ● The third bullet point is the most important IMHO, and should proceed everything else (+1) ● Lack of education resources ● Lack of education around data ● Education for Researchers, Data Repository Staff and Institutions (+2) ● who should manage access? ● "Who should manage access?" - Aboriginal language groups are not leading the capture and protection of sacred knowledge ● How do I know I have permission to use the data? (+4) ● deciding who are the right people ask in the first place (+1) ● In what ways can data be used? Are there specific rules/laws/cultural considerations/agreements in place? ● Lack of places (archives/repositories in which to put data (long term management, access control) ● Handling knowledge and access to knowledge that is collectively 'owned'. ● Access to knowledge- who is giving permission ● Some also say that because we are aware of this we are sometimes over cautious about information that should be promoted and public to educate everyone. (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Without appropriate controls, data can breach cultural protocol by viewing access and be misused. Trust is important but how is this really controlled? (+3) ● The CARE principles are important but can work at cross purposes to the FAIR principles. What's most important? Open data or control of access? (+3) ● Break the cycle of Indigenous research being hidden, inaccessible and not cared by Indigenous people. ● Missing data that everyone misses out to use and ● information is hard to find once inside an organisation - the world view of the person who stores the data is the world view needed to find it (+1) ● Where do I find the data? (+2) ● we don't know what data is held where ● Data is lost / unable to access ● has indigenous consultation ● Is Indigenous owned ● lack of involvement of Indigenous people to make any decisions ● The data ownership needs to be led by Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islanders for true data sovereignty (+1) ● Community ownership and led by community for whole lifecycle of research ● Understanding that indigenous people are needing more representation. This is a good start. ● centralising processes for consulting with community about the collection/use/reuse of their data. Would facilitate research. ● basically lack of involvement from the Indigenous peoples affects everything we do in the following ● Insufficient access for Indigenous communities to government data in general. ● "Insufficient access for Indigenous communities to government data in general." - Traditional Lore framework gaps in CARE/FAIR assessments ● Data accessibility ● Regulatory policies in Indigenous context (+1) ● The care and collection of of Indigenous knowledges ● Rapid pace of change re big data (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Policy and Technical Challenges (+1) ● Challenges around confidentiality in sharing data ● lack of international benchmarking ● We sometimes lack the methods to actually follow through on what is included in agreements ● How is gender responsibility Lore considered ● Data/knowledge/wisdom are separated artificially in Western ideas of data, which means what is and isn't Indig ● incorrect data and knowledge transfer (+2) ● Challenge might be defined so broadly that it's difficult to start, but then individual projects might be too granular to address the bigger concepts and issues ● where does the root of all of this come from? ● The translation of Aboriginal language can only be done by Aboriginal Traditional knowledge holders. ● Not sure if this can ever be achieved. Who will be contacted to get this information. Would be a tough to get all consent.
<p>Who does this challenge affect? (Who needs a solution?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researchers, ACCOS, Community, Government ● It affects everyone. Indigenous peoples, researchers, organisations, government departments (+1) ● Indigenous communities and Indigenous researchers (+2) ● researchers and Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people who want access to the knowledge - and/or to know what has already been collected ● Indigenous communities worldwide will benefit from this work. The more models and best practices the better. ● Indigenous people need this, however it will be a challenge for those organising this research. ● Indigenous peoples and societies on a global scale. (+1) ● This challenge affects Indigenous people and communities at all levels of aggregation and disaggregation. for example, it may affect the usefulness of data for statewide and national peak bodies ● affects beginning researchers and the population that is the topic of research +++ without much benefit. ● Demands on representatives of communities to address research-related questions - facilitated by a commons (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Indigenous research collaborators and participants ● Academia, Policy makers and all levels of govt ● Researchers, Policy makers, Government (+1) ● Organisations who need comprehensive data sets to develop policy positions ● Researchers, Unis/institutions ● As a researcher in social sciences, I think the challenge applies quite broadly. For instance, in common social sciences data like surveys or administrative data, or Census data that are representative of the whole population, including Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples. There is currently lack of consistence guidance on how this data should be used, including on projects/analyses that don't specifically focus on Indigenous people, but they are part of the dataset ● Future generations of researchers (+1) ● ACCOS and their clients are disadvantaged in the data game ● RE: Education & capacity building is needed by Indigenous & non-Indigenous people within: * Academic research orgs (unis, CSIRO, others) * Government (state & federal) organisations * GLAM sector * Private sector ● All government bodies and data collecting/holding institutions ● Everyone who uses the data and it affects whole community (+1) ● Many groups that intersect with Indigenous data and content that need protocols and guidance ● solution needed by anyone/organisation that wants to include Indigenous perspective in their work - should be everyone ● Civil society organisations and community groups ● "Indigenous business owners and operators" - Permission granting is problematic ● Ethics committees ● Everyone ● Indigenous business owners and operators

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What limitations are created by this challenge?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Aggregation of data that often minimises the specific region and need, lacks understanding of context. This reflects inaccurate projections of communities and needs, and can negatively influence policy reform. ● Lack of understanding of cultural context (+2) ● IP and ownership is removed when subjected to third-party navigation. Fragmented management strategies and irregular processes make it harder for communities and individuals to access (+1) ● Access to data is limited to those with specific technical skills and possibly narrow perspectives ● Institutional gatekeeping preventing access - attempts to do the right thing lead to over zealous protection ● Lack of access and recognition of the standards, lack of structure to direct changes reduces ability of change (+1) ● Historically the trust of collecting information from Indigenous people is a trust issue. Will they be able to view the data. ● Lack of trust and transparency between communities institutions, and researchers ● getting consensus on what is good data governance across all interested parties needs to include flexible and board communication styles to include everyone ● Limited understanding of the concept of IDS and IDG or how to operationalise the concepts at the organisational, community and sometimes government leveles (+2) ● fragmented and incomplete data ● Fragmentation of research and opportunities ● Lack of clarity around use/reuse (+2) ● lack of cultural/community protocol ● Cultural sensitivities mean some data should not be shared with some people in some circumstances - but it is valuable even though not sharable by all everywhere (+1) ● As discussed in the mediated data session, alot of data is coming through online in different platforms - produced by and about Indigenous people. Need to make sure we aren't just focussing on legacy data (+1) ● - Remember 'Open Scholarship' means language everyone can understand. Not just on the web and free of cost.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● There will be winners and losers ● community are being over researched and under involved (+2) ● Tribal sovereignties
<p>What could we achieve by addressing it?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● policies that align with Indigenous culture ● Better policy decision-making ● genuine community voices in policy decision making (+1) ● More Indigenous oversight of access to their knowledge, language and culture in archive/data holdings (+1) ● better governance structures (+1) ● Improving collective knowledge systems and contributing to global Indigenous people's data governance and sovereignty. (+1) ● Grass-roots guidance when it comes to ethical policies and governance led by Indigenous communities. (+1) ● greater engagement with indigenous data ● Everyone in Australia. Indigenous knowledge becomes an integral part of all future plans, projects and developments in Australia. This is an international issue - whatever we do - if done well - can help other countries acknowledge and respect their Indigenous knowledges (+4) ● Indigenous knowledges are integrated into all the data repositories used to solve the problems faced by people, communities, govt across Australia - Indigenous Knowledges are part of the solutions (+2) ● Clarity and comprehensive, appropriate supporting resources for education. (+1) ● Custodians of data sources that are not primarily Indigenous data - protocols and tools can help them better CARE for the Indigenous data they do have (+1) ● Community based research and Researchers (+1) ● "Community based research and Researchers' ' - Well stated. This I believe is part of the resolution. CBR through yarning and telling the real story-not one that they may think the non-Indigenous researchers want. ● Researchers having access to and more skilled in better practices ● Research organisations have an understanding of how data can be used, ultimately benefiting research with better outcomes (+2) ● Scientific organisations would benefit from a better understanding of positionality and the history (racism) of science as a discipline as it

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>would lead to better and more culturally appropriate science being done (+1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Shifting research and conversations away from a deficit perspective ● Better use of data across all sectors that ensures correct and appropriate data sets. It would also allow for better translation of data and optimise application. (+1) ● Research could have effective outcomes for the community if collaboration is achieved. Culturally safe and constructive and empowering outcomes (+1) ● developing cultural awareness ● corrections to misinterpretations. ● Improved recognition and understanding of Indigenous culture, knowledge and more for all Australians ● Facilitating repatriation ● Some level of return of data to knowledge owners/custodians, traditional owners, individuals and communities. Link to that knowledge may have been lost over time (+2) ● And once it's organised and geolocated etc, it makes it easier to identify which peoples it can be 'repatriated' to. ● protections to cultural knowledge (+2) ● the preservation of culture ● It can be achieved if we work together regardless as one, with utmost guidance by Indigenous community. ● greater confidence in use/reuse of indigenous data (+1) ● Framework for understanding what is indigenous data (+1) ● International networks of Indigenous researchers (+1) ● Get broader acceptance of sharing data and how to properly document it ● - Easy to meet metadata compliance standards, with required and desirable fields. (eg: title, description, nations/langs/peoples, geolocation, re-use and licence conditions, content warning); - this standard given credibility being both Indigenous lead and Uni endorsed.; - Custodians make themselves compliant. - Some initial work to get some major custodians of large amounts of information on board. - Badging for Indigenous data compliant organisations (like the

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>old W3c compliant web logos etc). - Custodians self register compliant data in an index.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● greater self-determination ● And some assistance for custodians/communities who are under-resourced to bring up to compliance. ● Access and analyse data even when on country ● Indigenous peoples' inherent rights and interests in data recognised and respected (+1)
<p>Who could be benefitted by addressing this challenge?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Most importantly, the Indigenous community, but also all researchers, government and other organisations working with services and infrastructure to support the Indigenous community. (+1) ● Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander community, researchers, government, ACCHOs, all users across the life cycle of the data ● the only benefit would be the research people. I'm not sure if it will benefit the indigenous people of the now, maybe the future generations. ● Social Sciences, Humanities, and the Arts for People and the Economy/Entrepreneurial (SHAPE) and the Indigenous community benefits from (+1) ● Hopefully Indigenous communities first ● community (+1) ● Communities can benefit by having greater visibility for planning, control over activities and increased opportunities to participate in spaces they arent (+1) ● Aboriginal and TSI Communities must be the f primary beneficiaries (+3) ● Closing the Gap ● There really is the potential for many beneficiaries of this. Government, business sector, Community, NFP, Research Institutions etc. How is the benefit/value considered, captured and protected? ● Research community but also general population ● We might act as a demonstrator for other communities that face similar challenges ● Global benefit. In that we set the standard for data control and use of First Nations. (+2)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Aotearoa New Zealand & Australia lead the world on Indigenous Data Governance & Indigenous Data Sovereignty scholarship. NB: Australia is waaaaay behind on practice (unfortunately). ● Technological and scientific advancement based on Indigenous Knowledge made clear by finding patterns in disparate data sets ● Indigenous data sovereignty (+1) ● everyone interested ● Arts and cultural sector (+1) ● GLAM sector ● Policy reformers, social policy reform, datasets, future health programing, future policy implementation (more complete data sets can improve outcomes). This can be represented in noting positive change in community growth and health development, or identify broader gaps previously missed by fragmented data sets. Can demonstrate community resilience and need, leading to greater outcomes from correctly guided implementation strategies that can offer positive individual outcomes. (+1)

Activity 2: Outcomes and opportunities

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What outcomes would be beneficial?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● indicators of how to use the knowledge respectfully, and within its original context, that is linked to all knowledge items (+3) ● Guidance or point to sources of appropriate metadata that supports Indigenous data sovereignty, discoverability, use, access, cultural controls, etc (+3) ● Fit-for-purpose cookbooks & 'how to' guides. It should be as easy to catalogue & share correctly tagged Indigenous data as make damper. (+2) ● Work on the Indigenous metadata bundle that is appropriate to the Australian context, so that it can inform the various metadata schemas used across disciplines. Collecting organisations can then use these metadata fields internally as well (+1) ● Standardising protocol for approaching communities ● Facilitating consultation processes with community

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Easier way to find the appropriate contacts within communities, especially when it comes to provenancing historical data (+1) ● Better skills at how to manage data gives Indigenous people more control over own data ● Partners (institutions/associations) developing curriculum and resources for Indigenous people to be trained in data science and other data fields so they can play a substantive role (+1) ● A resource that integrates the data issues with the methodology issues, so that applied researchers and community members can better understand what research questions and claims can be made with what type of data (+3) ● Promoting a more conscious awareness and thoughtful reuse of data and information is crucial, especially when dealing with historical data. It is essential to acknowledge the limitations inherent in historical data and to recognize its potential to perpetuate harm or pose a threat by reinforcing or creating unnecessary bias and skewed perspectives about Indigenous people across Australia. ● Guidance for researchers/users across different fields on using data on Indigenous people that were collected as part of whole-of-population data collections, such as Census data, government administrative data or nationally representative surveys like HILDA in the social sciences – are there any considerations here in the context of Indigenous Data Sovereignty for example? ● "Guidance for researchers/users across different fields on using data on Indigenous people that were collected as part of whole-of-population data collections," - there are considerations in terms of sampling strategies, which often appear to have been driven by issues of practicality, rather than of rigour ● Indigenous Data Sovereignty as core unit across disciplines and not restricted/offered to mob only (+3) ● Indigenous Data Sovereignty as undergrad degree or degree topic (+4) ● More Indigenous librarians to guide students at all levels in Universities and council libraries (+4) ● Guides/training for all post graduate students doing data-driven research (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● accessible through current systems utilised by high schools. They are the next researchers! (+3) ● Example information use/sharing agreements (+2) ● Would really love a guide to managing Indigenous data ● Culturally appropriate, online open resources (e.g., how-to videos, social media posts, Web pages) by & for Indigenous people involved in recording (collecting), using & sharing digital information. These resources must be done by Indigenous people with the support of technologists, but not led by (non-Indigenous) technologists. (+1) ● potentially a libguide type of resource that brings all information into on central location (for ease of access) ● accessible online resources (+1) ● Frameworks, guidelines, policies - examples of and guidelines for creation ● culturally responsive partnerships (+1) ● outcomes from research are made available to communities they come from ● Greatly benefit on greater access to Indigenous knowledge across the fields of research and industry. ● "Greatly benefit on greater access to Indigenous knowledge across the fields of research and industry." - language appropriate communication, in Aboriginal English, Aboriginal languages - pre, and post research. so then community people can see their names in academic papers that are written in their Aboriginal languages ● Creating communities of practice with Indigenous-led academia and scholars, industry and communities ● Nothing happens without trust ● Trust (+1) ● Trust and Transparency don't stop at institutions or researchers, but also with Archives and Repositories. ● That community have access to their knowledge/data collected (+1) ● Tools that are easy for communities to access (their own data), or provide input into improving the data where it may be inaccurate or inappropriate (+7) ● Clarification on what is the full scope of Indigenous data and how the protocols governing this data may vary depending on the form -

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>whether it is culturally protected lore through to less sensitive data - does this dimension interact with the principles and practices of data sovereignty?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● have AIATSIS somehow involved in overseeing access and care of the Indigenous knowledge/data (+2) ● setting up a governing body by Indigenous peoples ONLY ● Sector wide uniformity in policies, protocols etc. (+1) ● clarity on definitions ● Standards ● community engagement ● Legislative requirements to enforce Indigenous Data Sovereignty. (+1) ● People making Indigenous data think of sharing and preservation and reuse at time they save it - not an afterthought ● would love to have a First Nations person be able to assist with interpretation of the data. And be of the tribe that it originates from (+1) ● "would love to have a First Nations person be able to assist with interpretation of the data..." - Does this imply some kind of partnership between the person interpreting the data and the researchers/analysts who are undertaking analysis of the data? ● Consent forms that people don't just click through ● Understanding the TIME required to do this properly ● Ethics committees to respect the input of communities about process (+1) ● Stories, media articles, radio program featuring impact of Indigenous data sovereignty that increases general awareness ● A primer on Indigenous Web services (aimed at non-Indigenous full stack developers) Includes guidance on different world views, multi-lingual support (what can & cannot be supported), significance of colour(s), imagery, culturally appropriate terms (including spelling, referencing). This could be done by undergraduate digital communication students across 1 or more university Indigenous student programs. (+3) ● Innovation and CQI would be targeted, empowering and effective to benefit community and the owners of the data (+2) ● All areas of the research are relevant to those who participated.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What existing infrastructure/ activities could we build on?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● University Initiatives e.g. Indigenous Data Network, ATSDIA Protocols ● Research programs and indexes eg the Closing the digital gap index ● First Nations Descriptive Practice guidelines released by NSLA, CAUL, ALIA ● community research frameworks and some do exist. ie see Mithaka Research Framework (+1) ● Addressing Global Challenges with Indigenous Knowledge -United Nations ● The Uluru Statement of the Heart and VOICE (+8) ● The Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing (+7) ● Aiatsis "Yumi Sabe" platform. Yumi Sabe, a data platform showcasing the complexity and diversity of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples' research and culture. This data can then be accessed by Indigenous communities, researchers and policy makers to inform and improve policies. https://yumi-sabe.aiatsis.gov.au/YumiSabe@aiatsis.gov.au (+4) ● Maiam Nayri Wingara Principles (+9) ● AIATSIS core cultural learning ● "AIATSIS Code of Ethics" - Good idea Stand on the shoulders of those who have gone before ● "AIATSIS Code of Ethics" - absolutely!) ● Feasibility study for QLD Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander human ethics committee ● Indigenous Referencing Guidance from CAVAL https://members.caval.edu.au/media/images/Documents/CRIG/CACIK/CAVAL_Indigenous_Knowledges_Citation_Guide.pdf ● AIATSIS Code of Ethics (+4) ● IFLA - International version of GLAM ● CARE Principles (+7) ● NLA Indigenous Cultural and Intellectual Property ● Guidelines for First Nations Collection Description https://trove.nla.gov.au/work/255162661 ● Traditional knowledge labels and biocultural labels (+4) ● United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples Act (+4) ● ATSILIRN Protocols

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Wikipedia and Wikidata ● Location Index / Digital Atlas of Australia data platform (aus version of spatial Wikidata) ● Shameless plug: TLCMap Gazetteer (+3) ● OCAP (+1) ● New State Place Name Gazetteers ● Data donation and Digital platform social data projects at ADM+S - and the mediated data program proposal ● Lowitja Institute's Taking Control of Our Data: A Discussion Paper on Indigenous Data Governance for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander People and Communities - Lowitja Institute. ● ATSIHealth ● Austlang (+2) ● Indigenous metadata bundle (+1) ● Linked Data from the ABS: https://asgs.linked.fsd.org.au/dataset/asgsed3 ● Mayi Kuwayu Study ● True Tracks by Terri Jenke, see https://www.terrijanke.com.au/resources ● The IIIF framework provides support for multiple voices and multiple perspectives in both annotation implementation and in the exposure of annotations. ● Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA) provides an existing infrastructure for development and management of vocabularies. ● Individual components (IIIF, web annotation standards, SKOS vocabularies) are well known and well understood. Challenge seems to be the policy and governance framework. ● The International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) provides a standards based open protocol for flexible collaboration on the application of annotation across institutional repositories. ● Image Annotation Workbench (developed as part of CDL in 2023) provides an infrastructure for implementation of annotations to IIIF standards. ● Indigenous Research Ethics guidelines developed by the Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies ● indigenous research ethics committee (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Finding existing examples from other indigenous groups and adapting to an Aust context. How have they collated/presented the information? ● indigenous cultural intel property ● Sensitive data standards ● Indigenous Cultural Intellectual Property (+4) ● make ICIP principles binding (+3) ● On Country workshops and Aboriginal Cultural Sensitivity material that almost every university creates in-house - share and collate and use the descriptions/work of many already ● Relational work at the very beginning is so important. (+2) ● I grew up not knowing the meaning of any places around me. We recently made maps of the Bunya gathering and routes that go past my old house. Two days later QLD Ed Department proposes using them to teach maths to year 4 to 6 kids. Kids growing up with knowledge they tried to erase is a desirable outcome. (+8) ● Linking with current Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander organisations would be the first place to start. (+3) ● NCRIS facilities (all 26!!) (+1) ● API's can be opened up to allow multiple communities to expose annotations in culturally appropriate ways. ● Terry Janke's Indigenous IP guidelines https://www.terrijanke.com.au/resources

Activity 3: Roles and partners

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What other kinds of partners need to be involved?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community ● Community cultural Facilitators, MULTIPLE ● Community groups i.e. councils, community jury etc. ● For, By, With First Nations Community ● Indigenous elders, parents and community members ● The Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander community in general ● All Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander state and national peak bodies like NACCHO, VACCHO, QAIHC etc (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Indigenous peak bodies ● "AIATSIS" - AIATSIS, ANU, UOM and ARDC key partners of the IIRC Project ● AIATSIS ● Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander language centres - not just First Languages Australia because they do not represent all language centres ● Data Sovereignty Hubs at Universities (UniMelb, UTS, UQ etc.) ● TLCMap (+1) ● "NCRIS facilities" - Atlas of Living Australia ● Atlas of Living Australia (+1) ● AURIN ● CAUL - Council of Australian University Librarians - for capturing Indigenous collections and library records/metadata (+1) ● Large indigenous data holders of all sorts, e.g. ABS ● NCRIS facilities ● PHRN (+1) ● Possibly ONDC? (+1) ● Repository & System Vendors ● TERN ● Charity groups and organizations that add to data ● Co-design [research] approached need to be employed- again across level of government ● Health research community is asking for guidance- could be a specific focus ● Media - particularly Indigenous media channels, and national - as a partner to promote awareness and opportunities to collaborate ● NGOs ● Perhaps a focus group for projects. A working party for governance and input. Made up of local glam, Higher ed, teachers, community of course. Not just the big governing bodies. ● Regular mob doing everyday work.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What other expertise/resources would benefit the project?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● International First Nations colleagues who have experience with making IDGov and IDGov initiatives a reality (+1) ● Learning from other countries that are working in this space, esp NZ and Canada - we might not need to reinvent the wheel (+1) ● International treaties etc like UNDRIP, Nagoya, so we are in line with them ● International organisations in other countries that also work with Indigenous data (+1) ● Community Based Researchers. ● Indigenous scholars groups (+1) ● Expertise can be built and develop with ongoing technical/financial/infrastructure stability and continuity are crucial across levels of government. ● PIDs (+2) ● i4iOZ (+1) ● CDL Tools and methods ● RVA (+1) ● Research Vocabularies Australia ● Jobs for workers. To encourage Tech skills, there needs to be jobs for those who acquire them. (+3) ● Career progression for those working in the area ● Working/ collaborating with AIHW who receive an extremely large amount of data. (+2) ● The mediated data program would help provide access to digital platform data from Indigenous communities ● Translational research frameworks to apply ● The other RDC - People and Planet at the ARDC ● MORE TIME (+2) ● Research Consulting ● Vocabulary Development Consulting ● Consultation has many forms: visit elders; read books; go to conferences; watch Youtube clips; just have a chat.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Whose perspectives and input would make this project better?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Indigenous Ranger groups ● Indigenous Ranger groups working on country ● Indigenous scholars, social workers, teachers, elders and policy makers are needed to sit together. (+2) ● Indigenous scholars, students, community leaders and or Elders. (+2) ● Teachers from all grades (primary to high school) (+1) ● Those being researched. ● Communities organisations and groups involved in research data collection or collaboration (+2) ● Galleries Libraries Archives Museums (+1) ● AIATSIS Indigenous Research Exchange https://aiatsis.gov.au/research/indigenous-research-exchange (+1) ● Male and female community voices ● ARC and NHMRC and other funding bodies - include costs in research funding ● Indigenous linguists and language workers ● Lowitja Institute ● ACCHOs (+1) ● Researchers / practitioners working at the intersection of HASS and Science - don't exclude science just because this is a HASS project (+3) ● Terry Janke's website has many useful information resources to incorporate https://www.terrijanke.com.au/resources ● TDWG Biodiversity Information Standards (+1)

APPENDIX 2: WORKSHOP 2 RESPONSES

Outcome 1: Increase community engagement, input and access to research and its outputs

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander representation and engagement</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ensure that a variety of people are engaged with however also note that this may not represent all views (+1) ● An overarching statement being very clear around the diversity of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities and the validity of them all. (+2) ● Shared/open dialogue and acknowledging individual perspective ● This issue needs need consideration of the diversity of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander approaches to knowledge production and governance. 'Representation' is often a misnomer in this space. ● IIRF might be a consistent framework with which to manage accessible knowledge translation in multiple languages across multiple configurable cohorts. ● invite ideas from community and cater for diversity of responses ● Understanding that not everyone will want to be involved or be available but interested. ● How feasible is it to have greater Aboriginal & Torres Strait Islander people in these early co-design sessions? I think the tone of how to approach this should be set by them (vs me, a non-Indigenous researcher) ● Everybody engaged in a research project from admin to data scientists and of course the researchers, need to familiarise themselves with a community's history, FAIR and CARE information. Then begin your dialogue with the community. (+1) ● Communities being provided an opportunity to identify research needs and organisations to actively support efforts to answering them ● Academia to actively acknowledge the inputs, contributions and value of TO groups when publishing (eg. a community that permits you to conduct research on country like an IPA should be acknowledged in

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>the publications as without their support the research could not have occurred).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● We almost need a meta-wiki for the data catalogues with the background & research to date on a community ● Not all interested participants may have internet access (+3) ● Tailoring academic 'language' for the audience. ● We need to reach far beyond engagement and representation. The research development workflow needs to embed direct Indigenous leadership, co-design principles and Indigenous data governance structures. (+3) ● Allow alternative participation pathways eg phone message, sms, voicemail ● Creating understanding of ownership, access and rights in this space - helping communities to understand that they have a say. Feeding this into Policy / practice at an institutional level ● co-develop different kinds of IP/cultural knowledge protocols that institutions can offer ● make sure forum allows Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people to contribute in their own way, in their own time, they and their contributions are taken seriously and respected, ● Ensure that Institutions systems are responsive to the diversity of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities. ● co-design/ ● And how to mitigate against loss of 'knowledge' or data through non-English language. ● effective engagement means knowledge shared with Community needs to be local and relevant (+2) ● Acknowledging and accepting the time that this will take has to be part of planning. ● When is being Indigenous on a project ok too? ● Institutions develop an engagement framework in consultation with communities to ensure they are respectful and meets the needs of their communities.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All research projects should have finding allocated to remunerate community members for their time & also have Indigenous research on the project team (ideally from that community) (+2) ● Understanding that interest in and consent for research is fluid (+1) ● Respect for alternative knowledge paradigms is important ● Organisational policies often work in opposition to best practice and cultural appropriate research practices ● In the NT, many Aboriginal people would engage best in their mother tongue ● Representation on data access committees or data governance committees ● It might not be possible to engage with everyone. But better to create a proposed approach for people to break ● "It might not be possible to engage with everyone. But better to create a proposed approach for people to break" - Universities hold vast collections often broad datasets, where engagement is complex. ● Prepare reseach data in the course of its creation so that itcan then be archived and made accessible to the relevant Indigenous people (+1) ● Ensuring enough time for community engagement and communications, back and forth. Being clear on engagement model, including who and how decisions are made. ● Appropriate remuneration and benefits for First Nations communities working on projects ● Community consents and control practical considerations - These can end up being at a point in time and do need revision and active, ongoing care. Consents are usually given within a particular context and relationship. Those change, on all sides and then years later need to be reactivated which can often be challenging.
<p>Accessible knowledge translation of project outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Outputs should be defined between researcher and communiity at the early stages of research to ensure they are fit for purpose ● It would be useful to align reporting of outputs with the diversity of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities - to provide resources for analysing and reporting on data at varying levels of analysis, including cross-classified approaches

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research should contain positioning comments which are also explicit around Truth Telling. (+1) ● What are the benefits to Aboriginal communities? Research should always be about those communities and not contributions to researchers CV's. (+3) ● Consider accessibility of outputs from the initial design so they can be effectively shared ● Acknowledgment of this work within the current academic structures has to be fixed or there is a disincentive for researchers to do this. ● How to manage accessibility to culturally sensitive project outputs ● Some knowledge should not be shared to everyone in all circumstances. Editing that out when it becomes another medium (e.g. a movie of someone speaking) may be a challenge if not done during creation of work ● People dedicated to outreach and communication within the project. Create an outreach strategy and plan (+1) ● Clarification of the role of community input and data-driven decisions in theory formation ● Making sure the project has clear benefit to Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples from the get go ● Aboriginal people must always remain 'owners' of the data. (+4) ● CARE and FAIR (+1) ● Project co-design will ensure outputs are suitable, usable and appropriate for Community (+1) ● Make sure you have a binding contract with the community group, that provides them with community ownership and delineates where the data/project sits. (+2) ● manage multiple cohorts and their granular differentiation of access to content. using CMS and IIIF ● Where to store digital outputs. What technical/storage platform ● "Where to store digital outputs. What technical/storage platform" - this would be very beneficial to explore in detail ● data collection techniques appropriate for Community - including literacy and cultural protocols - to ensure outcomes are

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>understandable and are valid representations of the Knowledge that has been shared</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CMS infrastructure to manage content dissemination in multiple formats appropriate for audience ● Open access and ownership of research must remain by knowledge holders ● Need to define for whom it is being translated, and ask those people how to frame, what medium etc ● Stop using ICIP to block access by Indigenous people to material in their own language/heritage (+1) ● Use NTROs to disseminate. Also ask community participants how they want to see the outputs conveyed back to community (may be an exhibition on Country or a blog) (+2) ● presentation of projects/outputs developed historically
Network building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Respect & Reciprocity ● Community of practice (+1) ● How do we manage the size of the network and are case studies better (+1) ● Continued sharing of updates regarding the project in formats that are accessible to community (+1) ● Ensure the Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander participants are co researchers - name them in the publications and create opportunities for them to participate in projects they identify as being of interest to them rather than always being reactionary to others research ideas. (+2) ● Apply CARE principles ● Roles and responsibilities ● Safe and inclusive community ● Sustainable capacity-building and training opportunities are crucial. (+2) ● "Sustainable capacity-building and training opportunities are crucial." - all grants associated with research projects should have training built into the budget ● Mentoring and supporting Indig researchers and community members involved in research to attend events (conferences etc)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engaging Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people as facilitators that can link projects, researchers, organisations to Community - through their long and trusted relationships with that Community ● Use Austlang identifiers so the content can be found by speakers of that language (+1) ● appropriate timelines for projects - based on Community needs not researcher deadlines - this builds respect and helps Community support research into the future - and share their good experience with other Communities (+1) ● Provide a secure online environment to annotate and transcribe relevant manuscripts that are held in collecting institutions, so everyone can then know what is in them and what can be done with them (+1) ● How to manage the interaction of networks based on different commonalities. ● Don't use proprietary tools that lock heritage materials up for future users (+4) ● Leverage relevant UN Human Rights & Indigenous Peoples statements and resources. For example, the NAB Bank (to my surprise) worked on a Human Rights Impact Assessment framework (tool) with the support of the Australian Human Rights Commissioner. I believe there are some good lessons to be learned about HOW they did the project in terms of engagement, reference materials, workflow, systemic change, etc. CSIRO hosted a session on 15 Feb that was excellent & if you can review it, do so. ● See Human Rights Impact Assessment (HRIA): AI-informed decision-making systems in banking ● https://humanrights.gov.au/our-work/technology-and-human-rights/publications/hria-tool-ai-banking ● See also: CSIRO Australian AI Ecosystem Discoverability Platform Beta ● https://www.csiro.au/en/research/technology-space/ai/AI-capabilities-directory?start=0&count=12 ● See also: Final Report: Human Rights & Technology ● https://humanrights.gov.au/our-work/technology-and-human-rights/publications/final-report-human-rights-and-technology

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● See also: Guidance Resource: AI and Discrimination in Insurance ● https://humanrights.gov.au/our-work/technology-and-human-rights/publications/guidance-resource-ai-and-discrimination-insurance ● Internships, fellowships, on Country events, building a strong community of practice within and between organisations

Outcome 2: Support the appropriate governance of Indigenous data

APPROACH	RESPONSES
Indigenous data governance frameworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Link collections to governance in data descriptions, so viewers can learn about appropriate indigenous governance eg This collection governed by... (+1) ● Co-design approach with the utmost guidance from the community/knowledge holders who are involve on Indigenous data governance and development of frameworks/models (+5) ● Apply Indigenous Data Governance principles and practices retroactively where possible to facilitate interoperability across relevant datasets ● Needs to be considered whenever data is being collected in the design phase as well as how it will be stored and shared. ● For Aboriginal Housing NT, a lot of relevant data is held by government departments. So governments need to be on board. (NT Gov is not at all keen to share.) (+1) ● Be clear that there is significant loss in translation - produce two data sets - one in first language and the translated other. These two sets are critically important for those communities because they will be able to retrieve more knowledge at a later date. (+4) ● Ensure each community participates in identifying how access is controlled. ● Stop assuming Aboriginal people are not capable of high level cognitive function because of a lack of SAE. ● There needs to be some clear expectations around right to know and timelines that data stewards must follow to enact RTK (the recent

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>changes in the US as an example of where this can be very effective to drive change (+1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Any general framework being granular enough to accommodate needs of particular communities ● When FAIR principles are in conflict with CARE principles, CARE principles must take precedence. (+2) ● Who is the community? (+1) ● Need to be written by indigenous groups, or through indigenous support ● Indigenous data governance frameworks need to accommodate sometimes very diverse approaches to Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander approaches to knowledge production and governance. This is a fundamental challenge to accommodate diversity. (+2) ● Indigenous knowledge systems being part of the design of the framework ● Organisations often want a say in Indigenous research (e.g. co-design), which is in opposition to Indigenous-led Indigenous data governance/sovereignty ● Indigenous data governance frameworks must be mutable to accommodate changing community governance. In one well known community, senior women became knowledge-holders and custodians of initiated men's knowledge when those men were no long with us. Data structures need to reflect the agency of Indigenous communities to make changes to access restrictions; this is a fundamental challenge to traditional Western approaches to data management. (+2) ● co-design ● YES! This is needed. But what do they consist of? ● "YES! This is needed. But what do they consist of?" - This is the question we are seeking to answer, what elements and functions need to be included in frameworks? ● Consider a model that treats content as nodes that can be annotated by multiple actors with multiple voices and implement governance around access and visibility of both node and its annotations. ● frameworks that include systems and data creation

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "frameworks that include systems and data creation" -being familiar with the literature on this topic is also very useful with co-design ● IDG requires Indigenous people to be in decision-making positions. Having a policy/framework is not enough, it must also be reflected in employment & project management structures & benefit sharing (+2) ● tools to assist the ethical decision making process, people
Education and capacity building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Making sure that if/when using FAIR etc. as a base, that Indigenous-focused approaches like True Tracks help to inform frameworks ● Consider what it means to be 'data literate' - effectively using data to inform decision making. So think about what data people are already using or engaging with to provide opportunities to build capacity rather than making it something else people have to do. (+1) ● "Consider what it means to be 'data literate' - effectively using data to inform decision making" - data literacy is such a difficult one...it often feels like you need to be a data scientist to be across information and its curation...which seems at odds with HASS ● Consider a parallel process of aligning data-informed decision-making with data-informed theory-formulation. What is entailed in eliciting diverse views about relevant theory. There are risks in a predominantly data-driven approach to research and decision-making ● What data are you wanting to improve capability with? IT is government data, data that is shared by individuals at services, Indigenous data? This will determine how literacy can be enhanced. ● Build capacity in communities, in ways that benefit the community ● The feedback loop is crucial - well-informed people make good governance decisions which show more people the value of becoming informed. ● Reaching curators of Indigenous data who don't think of themselves as curators, or what they have as data. How to provide education to get them to the table at all? (+1) ● comms/education at Director and Senior levels on importance of metadata as getting their ok for project funding is critical ● Care Principle applications across different systems ● Include youth from communities as researchers in training. (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Training for Communities be included in budgeting. (+1) ● The summer school was great, would be good to implement from new Undergrad students and onward - get them thinking about it from the beginning of their higher education journey ● Create basic resources that clarify & build shared understanding of the FAIR and CARE principles ● Educating governments on how good Indigenous data governance can support better use of deidentified data across departments ● Commence framing Aboriginal communities beyond the deficit. ● HASS & Indigenous RDC Computational Summer School (+1) ● "HASS & Indigenous RDC Computational Summer School " - I learnt so much from this gathering!! ● Education and capacity building must involve both knowledge system (traditional & western views) to address the issues at hand and working side by side. ● Communities co-design and co-facilitate training with nominated champions in each community to continue the education and capacity building ● Indigenous peoples are forced to have an understanding of non-Indigenous people, while non-Indigenous people often have zero understanding of Indigenous peoples. The people most in need of education and increased capacity here is non-Indigenous people (+1) ● Researchers need training from the outset on IDG, across all disciplines ● engage Community people at all levels of project - mentoring and training to run own projects - mentoring to facilitate/translate between Western views and their local views ● Consider creating a plan with goals around who you want to reach, and how you will reach them ● Important to also build capacity of ethics review board members & other forms of peer review so research that doesn't follow IDG frameworks is flagged (+3)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Accessible and appropriate data stewardship and global collaboration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● working together is a key and co-design/CBPR/Ethnographic approach while connecting globally. ● FAIR without longterm data curation repositories is not FAIR (+6) ● In consultation with global communities who have more mature systems and leaders of our own Communities, and expertise of IDG network, ask what this might mean for the future. Then consult with engineers after proper collaboration is done. ● Make systems work from an Aboriginal perspective instead of always expecting Aboriginal communities to be the ones to change... (+1) ● What does stewardship mean when institutions are in control and not communities - what does community control/access actually look like? (+3) ● Let communities control this - too much is being appropriated! (+2) ● Make sure there is a mechanism for data that is prvded by Indigenous people is able to be continued to be accesed by those people and also results or findings are shared. ● Indigenous lead ● easy access to what has been collected in the past, and what they will be shared ● How to determine who the relevant Indigenouspeople are to decide on a particular collection's access rights? ● "How to determine who the relevant Indigenouspeople are to decide on a particular collection's access rights?" - Approaches for these problems has to be part of a governance framework. ● "How to determine who the relevant Indigenouspeople are to decide on a particular collection's access rights?" - A collection of health or employment data may involve many different people ● Work with orgs like GIDA, Maiam nayri Wingara, Indigenous Archives Collective etc that are Indigenous-led, global and leading work around IDS/IDG/ICIP in data steward spaces ● Centralised portals, tools, repositories for handling data ● "Centralised portals, tools, repositories for handling data" - Centralised maybe, but often repos need to be distributed for stewardship / governance / funding reasons maybe "concentrated" is

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>a better word than centralised. And with STANDARDISED metadata and interfaces For interop</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Centralised portals, tools, repositories for handling data" - Interoperability rather than centralisation? ● Indigenous control of what is shared and stored. Including the right to change/edit knowledge at any time = means easy access to data. ● "Indigenous control of what is shared and stored. Including the right to change/edit knowledge at any time = means easy access to data. " - Just noting that changing data is not FAIR compatible -- data needs to be identified and STABLE for research though this may be at odds with cultural requirements ● Must be aware of community intellectual property, explanatory notes and detailed discussions with community in a language that they understand. This may include need for translators. ● Do not support international collaboration because it loses focus on the Australian problem ● The custodian often doesn't have a mechanism to reliably control their data. ● "The custodian often doesn't have a mechanism to reliably control their data." - in addition data platforms are unreliable, sometimes temporarily funded...there are so many variables ● There is a lot we can learn from Indigenous communities in other countries that are already doing this work (+1) ● the world view of the person storing the data is the world view needed to find it again - we need different views considered when collecting and storing data and knowledge ● Importance of working with Pacific neighbours on repatriation of materials, support for locating relevant records in Australian institutions (+1) ● Who are the potential custodians of shared data? Government, NGO, Indigenous organisations? Can all these different potential custodians actually be supported?

Outcome 3: Create standards for Indigenous data, metadata and research

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Indigenous-led standard setting</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● This system must be Aboriginal/Torres Strait Islander community friendly and not designed to fit a 'system'. (+1) ● Agreement on high-level or minimum standards may be possible, although difficult to get agreement with so many stakeholders (+2) ● "Agreement on high-level or minimum standards may be possible, although difficult to get agreement with so many stakeholders" - Agreement on process may be a more realistic aim. ● How, who and what Aboriginal folk will be included in this? (+1) ● Engage with people from a variety of backgrounds right from the design phase ● Consultation, consultation and consultation - with a diverse range of Aboriginal communities (not just researchers) (+4) ● Identify relevant participants (+1) ● There will likely be pushback from non-Indigenous people about using these standards over other established (non-Indigenous) standards ● "There will likely be pushback from non-Indigenous people about using these standards over other established (non-Indigenous) standards" - It can be both. It is possible to use existing standards and add additional metadata that is specific to communities' worldviews & needs ● Indigenous -led standards principles/working on four R's (respect, relevance, reciprocity and responsibility) process/ designed and led by Indigenous governing bodies as well as working ethically and culturally. (+3) ● ICIP - building from True Tracks - community-focused guide as well as staff-focused (+2) ● Specified period of time, clear charter and regular meetings with transparency and communication processes (+1) ● Include Indigenous peoples on the research team from different organisations ● specific goals - avoid drift ● MOUs between community and collecting institutions that have guidelines for metadata standard (+2)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adopt Indigenous research methodologies in the research design (+2) ● There are many Indigenous views across Australia - sometimes very different - how do we incorporate them all - including at a Community level? (+1) ● Have an information pack for the Community as a beginning. Provide the Community with knowledge around metadata, labelling etc so that they can then ask informed questions. This takes time and goes back to careful relational work. This must precede any further conversations about data management, governance etc. ● What skills and knowledge on data do you need to deliver this work? Is it Indigenous with a data background? (+1) ● I'm imagining a workshop with remote Aboriginal people about standards. It could work, and would be valuable, and you need to have this input. But it would take a good while to develop a shared understanding of the concepts. I'm sure you know this. ● https://www.newcastle.edu.au/our-uni/indigenous-commitment/indigenous-cultural-and-intellectual-property-protocol ● the whole notion of 'standard' is problematic and not sure how it can be applied? ● "the whole notion of 'standard' is problematic and not sure how it can be applied?" - The aim is to use 'standards' to make data easier to find across institutions. The key is to balance standards with nuanced needs of each community.
Define cultural metadata standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interoperability of Metadata with and data that is culturally sensitive. How to approach and collected metadata to present or not present ● This should be in response to the knowledge or data... ● Standards for access control and acknowledgement can be challenging without exposing personal details (which can in turn be considered sensitive data) ● Balance Indigenous knowledge with GLAM and academic terminology to enhance data findability, searchability, and analysis. In a culturally safe environment (+5) ● If a standardised approach was available then methods for enforcing information use agreements could develop more and be trusted/proven

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● existing definition/projects of cultural metadata standards - UNESCO and CIDOC (International Committee for Documentation) work on creating broader conceptual models and guidelines for cultural metadata ● Again, a real challenge in this space is designing a system that is not prescriptive, but can accommodate diversity in ways of creating and managing knowledge. (+1) ● "Again, a real challenge in this space is designing a system that is not prescriptive, but can accommodate diversity in ways of creating and managing knowledge." - excellent point. not sure how cultural metadata cannot be prescriptive...as isn't that what it is? ● Adding onto the GLAM approach: Guidelines for First Nations collection description by Tui Raven https://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-3250767341/view (+2) ● Is this language, place, clan, and is it related to cultural knowledge ● General standards may be developed but should be flexible enough to extend and adapt to local practices and knowledge frameworks and accommodate different requirements (+4) ● An approach to managing the multiple voices in this space is to treat content as a node with annotations. In this way metadata on content and metadata on annotations might be managed separately under different governance regimes. Cohorts and actors within those cohorts might annotate with bespoke vocabularies. Visibility of those annotations would be governed by those cohorts/actors. (+3) ● "An approach to managing the multiple voices in this space is to treat content as a node with annotations". In this way metadata on content and metadata on annotations might be managed separately under different governance regimes. Cohorts and actors within those cohorts might annotate with bespoke vocabularies. Visibility of those annotations would be governed by those cohorts/actors." Tools for collaborative annotation are very valuable. (+1) ● Metadata standards for Content nodes needs SKO compliance ● Guidelines for First Nations collection description by Tui Raven. (+1) ● Not sure RVA, as it is currently constituted, has the required flexibility.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● TK Labels are a good example of this. Metadata is broadly grouped under attribution, protocols and permissions. (+4) ● Operationalise the Indigenous Metadata Bundle ● Annotation vocabulary standards might need to be more flexible than SKOS compliance. ● Are there any examples we can leverage off to support understanding metadata needs? ● Data catalogue and core/standard metadata fields would be invaluable. Limited opportunities to change cataloguing & documentation standards within institutions as can require extensive data work that's not readily funded. So these can't change all the time. Working with groups of institutions with similar datasets/collections is key for this as often have the same cataloguing systems. ● Persistent identifiers to external databases and terms ● Provision of education & comms at Council/Board/Director levels at institutions on the importance of time on metadata, not a subject that is exciting or attracts funding.
<p>Define classifications and licensing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Find balance between licencing and end user accessibility with in a culturally safe environment. Eg user accounts, accessibility, licencing, presentation of outputs ● While the Uluru Statement of the Heart still in our mind, it is now time to develop a solid classification and licensing for Indigenous data/visual data recordings with the aim of protecting traditional knowledge as well as providing economic outcome for the community (+1) ● Consider the best mechanism for sharing data with communities. For example what if Internet access is not guaranteed? Perhaps needs to be nuanced for each community? (+2) ● Data sharing agreements. Process and policy. Maybe be required rather than licences due to sensitivity of indigenous data - requires more details than a simple licence, more rules for sharing (+1) ● Is this a request from the wider Aboriginal community? It might be that they would prefer something else?

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consideration that cultural metadata standards may need to vary by state/region - there might not be a 'one size fits all' approach. Once the state/region-based standards are in place, there can always be some form of linking/translation mechanism that can be applied for external use ● Is there a danger here of making access even more difficult (at least in some cases)? Probably! (+4) ● "Is there a danger here of making access even more difficult (at least in some cases)? Probably!" - Yes!! This is already happening. The NLA has closed down access for Aboriginal people by citing its ICIP policy ● How can licences be enforced? ● Shouldn't this be based on Aboriginal knowledge systems, epistemologically and ontologically? (+1) ● "Shouldn't this be based on Aboriginal knowledge systems, epistemologically and ontologically?" - so not one system but many? ● Protection is important and appropriate, but don't forget delivering benefits. Licensing should support the ability to generate new insights and solutions. Closing the Gap (+1) ● Should we be ratifying the Nagoya Protocol? (+1) ● Does this include authentication models? ● Look at ICIP Protocols: See Newcastle Uni

Outcome 4: Provide training and guidance

APPROACH	RESPONSES
Development of training and upskilling resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Types of resources that can be revisited and referred to over time. (+2) ● Mixture of delivery models (+4) ● "Mixture of delivery models " - online is very challenging.....face to face engagement and so you can ask questions in person ● Ensure clarity between 1. Governance by Indigenous people over data; 2. Governance by Indigenous peoples over Indigenous data and 3. Governance by any type of person over Indigenous data (+1) ● Definitions of terms (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Caters for non academic recipriants (+1) ● Build better tools for creating archive-ready data, especially for small agencies like language centres, keeping-places, who need to describe material they are creating (+2) ● cookbook model ● Need to try to embed training and capacity-building into other training. Community are overloaded with training, much of which leads no-where - to qualifications, to jobs etc. So don't add extra burden of training where it can be embedded in existing frameworks - e.g. land and sea Country management activities. (+2) ● "Need to try to embed training and capacity-building into other training." - especially if the implementation and impact may not be sustained or fruitful ● peer to peer learning is what we are missing which should start from primary, high school and to higher education. (+3) ● "peer to peer learning is what we are missing which should start from primary, high school and to higher education." - yes we should not be starting this journey at University ● Adoption of mainstream open-source CMS framework to maximize existing skills eco-system ● How to collect or use data in a strengths based way, not deficit ● Includes traditional and non-traditional resources ● A summit of Community workers first up. Collect ideas of what does and does not work. Perhaps consult education experts who work in Communities for their best learning design methods . Indigenous teachers, learning designers and teaching assistants. (+1) ● If providing training with PBCs, then it may be useful to consider training targeted at other community and community-controlled organisations outside the PBCs - say, health, education, family services. there may be different decisions about data interoperability depending on the organisation type ● Info sessions with PBCs/Land Councils about what the training is and the benefits to the communit (+1) ● Field examples and case studies are very important to see the "people behind the data" in any training (+2)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Field examples and case studies are very important to see the "people behind the data" in any training" - demonstrating what is possible in an applied way is so helpful ● Develop training modules for those embarking on data collection and sharing. These will look very different to training for those who have legacy data collected/shared with bad practice. ● Introduction VET courses ● Recognizing that the spectrum of knowledge on what is data is broad. That Indigenous people do work with and understand the basics. (+1) ● Checking what's already out there, retooling as needed - looking to related resources (+1) ● pay for Elders for intergenerational knowledge transfer within Communities (+2) ● Focus on rollout of systems that provide in app support for annotation, vocabulary customization and digital publishing to generate outputs driven by cohorts and their interest communities rather than disconnected processes. ● Adoption of open source frameworks such as IIF to maximise existing tooling.. ● I found out that my institution has a line item for payment of those participating in research (Elder, knowledge holder, community member). I have since incorporated this in my budgets. It is a small but appreciated gesture. (+2) ● Target audiences defined and people reached effectively at the right time ● Availability of self-paced tutorials, eg the FAIR data training modules on ARDC ● Key blockages within a GLAM institution can often be down to use of technical jargon and needing introductory skills for a broad range of backgrounds. Often very challenging for staff to consider or learn from other fields (eg science) which can seem impenetrable for humanities trained staff. ● Staff are usually very keen to learn but need to have practical implications for it to be useful, seeing how it is done in another context/institution is very helpful. As is hearing directly from

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>community, knowledge holders as to the importance and benefit to them.</p>
<p>Hands-on Indigenous Data Governance training</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Recognition of IDG Frameworks for varying organisations. Understanding how each of these will vary due to the differing perspectives. eg, community, local governance, state government, federal government, commercial organisation/company, university.. etc ● training by indigenous people for indigenous people (+3) ● "training by indigenous people for indigenous people" - Snowball training? Where community members who have done the training and put it into place for the benefit of their community are then supported to become trainers for other communities. This ensures that we are building a strong base of SMEs relating to Indigenous knowledge management. (+1) ● Embed governance in CMS workflows rather than rely on policy compliance. ● Tailored to different types of data - e.g. health data and language data pose different problems. (+4) ● "Tailored to different types of data - e.g. health data and language data pose different problems." - the definition of data is so interesting and would therefore determine who instructs who ● Training on what to do with data that has been collected already under previous ethical agreements that don't allow sharing. How can these be updated so the community can access? (+7) ● What can we learn from governments who are going through the process of developing IDG Frameworks? ● "What can we learn from governments who are going through the process of developing IDG Frameworks." - the IDN has been working closely with several government bodies/departments in assisting the development of said resources. Levi has specifically contributed largely to the design of NIAA's first iteration on their forward coming framework: https://www.niaa.gov.au/indigenous-affairs/closing-gap/implementation-measures/aps-wide-framework-indigenous-data-and-governance (+2)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● If only there was a national agency that could hold Indigenous materials and make them accessible in a timely way and without blocking access to Aboriginal people (+2) ● acknowledging the basic lack of understanding around what governance is (+3) ● "acknowledging the basic lack of understanding around what governance is" - Or even about data itself - see data literacy in previous points. ● for Indigenous and Non-Indigenous. There is a lack of understanding that goes broadly across society. ● If Indigenous people are partners from the outset, in defining the schemas etc, then the training part will be a lot easier. Can we develop a relational system rather than an object-based one? (+8) ● the term governance in itself if a problem and shuts people out immediately ● Greater recognition of what counts as Indigenous data, especially in science (+1) ● Greater understanding needed by organisations about their national and international obligations for Indigenous data governance ● "Greater understanding needed by organisations about their national and international obligations for Indigenous data governance" - Yes! And greater understanding for Indigenous communities/people about their rights according to those same international and national statements. Also organisational commitments (RAP plans, ICIP policies etc) (+1) ● Should be for researchers/organisations as well as for communities who are often providing the data so they know their rights. (+2) ● with my 21 years of experience working alongside Indigenous Elders and the community - hands-on training on data governance should combined with theoretical practices with a holistic perspective with outcome directed back to the community. (+2) ● "Should be for researchers/organisations as well as for communities who are often providing the data so they know they rights." - perhaps advocacy might be possible through Aboriginal Corporation boards

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Focus on a core skill transfer of annotation of content nodes and cohort/actor driven publishing of annotations on nodes. This extensible skills set is consistent across cohorts.
Supportive learning networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● There are many groups, organisations and government departments looking at gaining skills in Indigenous Data Governance so a shared place/resource/toolkit would be useful or a Community of Practice. ● Accessibility to face to face and collaborative sessions. Eg round table and knowledge sharing (+1) ● "Accessibility to face to face and collaborative sessions. Eg round table and knowledge sharing" - in safe spaces such as those created by IDN and ARDC ● Health networks may already be striving for collaboration in WA ● Recognition that all the sectors are interconnected. Housing and health and education and employment and... (though the data is often separated by 'function') (+1) ● A suite of multi-modal learning materials, made with various communities. Accessible online or to be downloaded to I-Pads. See Lesley Acres' (at UQ) work in this area. (+2) ● Supportive learning networks needs to be integrated (not separate) across levels of industry. ● mentorship programs (+1) ● "mentorship programs" - https://ardc.edu.au/article/introducing-liam-jensen-the-ardcs-new-indigenous-intern/ ● Engaging the next generations as well! (+1) ● We need a National Indigenous researcher network. (+1) ● "We need an National Indigenous researcher network" - Would be interested to hear the scope of such a network; eg (1) searchable register - ID, Name, location, research interest, contact details, preferred method of contact, or (2) events, gatherings, sharing and contributing knowledge, process and key learnings. What would key functions be? Connecting, (3) learning, discovery, sharing; other? ● Can Indigenous people make Ombudsman complaints about agencies that refuse timely access to heritage records? Especially if it is the stated core business of the agency to make material available. (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Can Indigenous people make Ombudsman complaints about agencies that refuse timely access to heritage records?" - That would be a contribution to Indigenous data governance writ large, publish what rights people have and provide a contact point (email, name, role at a specific agency).